

Linking Node Communities to ELIXIR Communities

ELIXIR Italy All Hands Meeting 2023

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ELIXIR Communities – connecting infrastructure & life science experts

Formed around domain experts in ELIXIR Nodes (including non-ELIXIR partners)

Provide a mechanism for long-term collaborations with other ESFRIs and large-scale initiatives

Drive service developments in the ELIXIR Platforms

Provide a framework to develop and maintain community standards

The ELIXIR Communities Handbook tells you what a Community is, who can join, what the benefits are, and how Communities are structured.

Concrete points about ELIXIR Communities

- Must be directly linked to ELIXIR priorities as represented in the ELIXIR Programme and the activities of the ELIXIR Platforms
- Need strong representation from members of ELIXIR Nodes (target is a minimum 10)
 - Currently 5 (or 6)+3 possible
 - Some uncertainty remains
- Community should aim for three co-leads, ideally from different Nodes. This can formally be resolved once the Community is approved.
- We encourage links between different Communities and between Communities and Platforms

The purpose of Communities

More broadly ELIXIR Communities:

- Bring together domain specific experts across the Nodes
- Capture user needs into formal requirements
- Improve interaction and contact with user communities in our Nodes
- Drive the development of services (standards, tools, workflows, their uptake in & across Platforms, help prioritise work)
- Demonstrate broad impact of the infrastructure contribution to the users
- Help ELIXIR to demonstrate that the national services are global leaders

Additionally ELIXIR Communities are based, amongst others, on the following principles

- They will increasingly be the visible face of ELIXIR to the user community (working bioinformaticians; life scientists using large amounts of data)
- They must be long-term, not limited in temporal scope (subject to regular review)
- They must have strategic importance to the future development of ELIXIR
- They must have broad scientific importance and relevance
- Their membership must be drawn predominantly from within Nodes and must be led from within ELIXIR Nodes (Nodes are encouraged to widen coverage where there is an opportunity within the country that is not encompassed by a node)
- They must demonstrate Node support.

Community benefits

- Face-2-Face (F2F) Meeting
- White paper (for emerging Communities)
- Access to Implementation Study Funding
 - Initial Community Implementation Study
 - Community-led Implementation Studies
- Network, Interaction and Visibility
 - Collaboration
 - All Hands Meeting
- Communication, Outreach and Branding
 - Website
 - Community mailing lists
 - Online Presence/Branding
 - Webinar Support
- Scientific Support
 - Hub Technical Coordinators
 - Funding Opportunities
 - SAB & HoN review
 - Career Development
 - Impact Assessment
- Additional Support
 - Shared folder
 - Zoom/Online meeting Support/Guidelines
 - Communities (meeting) Calendar
 - Slack

Subject to minor changes: 2024-2028 Scientific Programme

Community contributions and responsibilities

Every established ELIXIR Community is expected to undertake the following activities:

- Three Community calls per year (organised by the Community, inviting the whole Community)
 - An agenda/meeting minutes needs to be available for all Community members for each call
- Annual Meeting (F2F or virtual)
- Supply content to maintain the website up to date (at least annual updates)
- Continued effort working towards the Community aims (as defined in the white paper goals), or provide a published update of the Community goals
- Community co-lead sharing updates during Programme TC's (every two months)
 - Presentation at Programme TC's (when called upon)
- Three to five year internal peer-review, when called upon

Encouraged contributions

- *All Hands Meeting attendance (by at least one Community co-lead/Community representative)*
- *Contribution to the ELIXIR All Hands meeting (e.g. workshop application, if part of the programme)*
- *Application to Implementation Study Calls*
- *Contribution to the ELIXIR webinar programme*
- *Participation in external Grant Proposals*

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ELIXIR Communities – the maturity journey

ELIXIR Communities follow a path as they progress towards maturity.

17 ELIXIR
Communities

Community resources

- The ELIXIR Communities [Handbook](#)
 - <https://f1000research.com/documents/12-69>
- [Communities Poster](#)
 - <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119415.1>
- ELIXIR Communities webinar
 - [Recording](#)
 - [Slides](#)

ELIXIR's Communities Team

Communities are supported by the ELIXIR Hub through the Communities Team.

Every Community has a direct contact point at the ELIXIR Hub, to support with day-to-day activities.

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ELIXIR Communities – Creation Cycle (HoNs agreed 07/2017)

3. Individual HoNs also consider if they have members who could participate

(final) white paper draft	Community → Katharina/Hub
Hub Review	→ publication in KCU
2 months	Consultation of white paper with the community
White paper presentation at HoNs	Positive answer
→ white paper publication F1000 & Implementation Study preparation	
Implementation study draft	Revision from Hub, in consultation with platform leads
Feedback to Community	Final Implementation study (Susanna checks/works on financial overview)
Implementation Study presented at HONs	Positive response
→ Implementation Study presented to Board	
→ Approval → Implementation Study start (official)	

Subject to change:
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Becoming an ELIXIR Community member

- Join the Community group and mailing list
 - <https://elixir-europe.org/communities>
 - choose your Community of choice
 - start receiving update emails
 - join their regular calls
 - get engaged
- Possibly join a Commissioned Service/join a F2F/hybrid meeting

[Home](#) » [How we work](#) » [Communities](#) »

Biodiversity Community

Biodiversity represents the full spectrum of organisms on Earth, at population, community, and ecosystem levels. The loss and decline of biological diversity are recognised by scientists and the public as a critical challenge for humankind to address.

Addressing this global crisis requires knowledge of the diversity of life on Earth, how that diversity functions and interacts, and how it responds to changing environmental pressures. This is why research that transforms our understanding of the variety of life on Earth, at phenotypic or genetic levels, is so important.

[Join this Community](#)

Questions?

Thank you! Get in touch!

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